

The Effectiveness of Using Short Story to Improve Students' Vocabulary Mastery

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Abstract

This research aims to find out the effectiveness of using short story to improve students' vocabulary mastery at the grade X students SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera in the academic year 2018/2019. The design used in this research was true-experimental design. The researcher involves random assignment of participants into two groups, experimental and control. Both groups are administered both a pretest and a posttest, but the treatment is provided only to experimental group. The researcher conducted this research from January until March 2018 in SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera. The subject was all of the students in X grade. The researcher divided into two classes. Each class consists of 20 students. In collecting the data, the researcher use test. The tests were given in pre-test, and post-test. The researcher analyzed the mean score of each test to find out the improvement of students' vocabulary mastery. The researcher conducted the action the students' vocabulary mastery increased optimally. It could be seen from the category of test in control class and experimental class. The category of pretest control class students' score was 6, 65. The category posttest control class students' score was 7, 65. While the category of pretest experimental class students' score was 6, 15 and the category of posttest experimental class students' score was 8, 45. After applying the action the researcher was able to improve the students' vocabulary mastery. The students were able to take the word meaning based on the context. By using short story in teaching vocabulary, students could easily understand and memorize new vocabulary.

Keywords: *short story, vocabulary mastery, true-experimental design, new vocabulary*

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1. Introduction

In communication, vocabulary is very important in the process of conveying and receiving information in the community. Vocabulary is a basic tool that is owned by someone who will learn a language because vocabulary functions to form sentences, express the contents of thoughts and feelings perfectly. According to the meaning of vocabulary, Soedjito (1992:1) "gives the following understanding of vocabulary: (1) all words contained in a language. (2) The word used in a science. (3) The wealth of words owned by a speaker. (4) A list of words compiled by a dictionary accompanied by a brief and practical solution" based on this opinion it can be concluded that vocabulary is all words contained in language. In addition, vocabulary is all words that are owned by someone who contains all the information about the meaning and usage of words in language.

In correlation with acquiring vocabulary, researcher wants to develop students' vocabulary by using short stories. A short story as the name implies, shows the short nature, both the events revealed, the contents of the story, the number of actors, and the number of words used". According to researcher short stories is very important to develop students' vocabulary, because the words are easier to understand, short story also liked by the students. Short stories can reduce anxiety and help students to be more relaxed in reading English texts.

In student's activities in the classroom, most students feel bored with the teaching and learning process because the learning material is less fun. Severe learning activities affect the way children overcome their boredom and fatigue. Excessive burdens and time for learning can make students become tired and tired.

The researcher was interested in conducting this research because there were other researcher who had carried out this research namely Hayati (2015) with the titles Using Short Story To Improve Students' Vocabulary Achievement of the Grade IX Students of SMP Negeri 6 Pangsid. The result of the study is teaching vocabulary with short stories can improve students' vocabulary. That is why researcher wants to apply the same research but different research sites, namely at SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera.

Before conducting this study, researcher interviewed an English teacher at SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera by using phone call on Saturday, September 12, 2018. The aim is to know the improvement of students' vocabulary in teaching and learning process in the classroom, especially in teaching and learning vocabulary by using short story to improve student's vocabulary mastery. Based on the interview, the teacher said "that there were still many students of SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera who could not understand the text that given by teacher" (example: recount text, descriptive text, narrative text, etc). The reason is that SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera especially grade X students of SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera has a limited/low vocabulary. Therefore, the researcher is interested in conducting the research to improve student's vocabulary with the title "The Effectiveness of Using Short Story to Improve Student's Vocabulary Mastery in SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera".

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Vocabulary

The understanding of vocabulary is widely expressed by experts but basically the understanding is complementary. Based on Indonesian Big Dictionary, vocabulary is words or the number of words a language has. This opinion is in accordance with the opinion expressed by Tarigan (2011) that vocabulary is words which are treasury of a language. Soedjito (1992:1) "gives the following vocabulary limitations: (1) all words contained in a language. (2) The word used in a science. (3) Word wealth owned by a speaker. (4) A list of words compiled by a dictionary with a concise and practical solution" according to Kridalaksana (2015) "vocabulary or lexicon, are as follows: (1) Language component that contains all information about the meaning and usage of words in language. (2) The wealth of words that a speaker has the author of a language. (3) A list of words arranged like a dictionary, but with a brief and practical explanation".

Based on some of these opinions it can be concluded that vocabulary is all words contained in language. In addition, vocabulary is all words that are owned by someone who contains all the information about the meaning and usage of words in language.

Vocabulary mastery is very important in language, the richer the vocabulary possessed by a person is the greater the person's skills in language (Tarigan, 2011). Vocabulary mastery can be divided into two groups: receptive and productive vocabulary mastery

Receptive mastery is the process of understanding what is spoken by others, receptive is defined as passive mastery.

Productive mastery is the process of communicating ideas, thoughts, and feelings through linguistic forms. Vocabulary mastery in activities and daily life has a very large role, because the thoughts of a person can only be clearly understood by others if expressed using vocabulary.

2.2. Short Story

Understanding short stories has been made and expressed by literary experts, and writers. Obviously it is not easy to make definitions about short stories. Even so, the following will be explained by the understanding of short stories expressed by leading literary and literary experts

Short stories are stories that limit themselves in discussing one of the elements of fiction in the smallest aspect. Short for a short story not because the form is much shorter than the novel, but because the problem aspect is very limited (Sumardjo and Saini, 1986). Short stories are one form of fiction. Short stories as the name imply, show a short nature, both the events revealed, the contents of the story, the number of actors, and the number of words used. This comparison is related to other forms of prose, such as novels.

As the name implies, short stories can be interpreted as short prose-shaped. The short size in this school is relative. The short size here is finished reading in one sitting, which is approximately less than an hour. As for Sumardjo and Saini (1986), this short measure is based more on the limitations of the development of its elements. Short stories must have a single and complex effect.

Understanding the short story put forward above are a small part of the understanding of short stories. Some notions of short stories that have been put forward by the experts above, the author succeeds in concluding the notion of short stories in isolation. A short story (short story) is an essay in the form of prose fiction that is read out once sitting, the purpose of reading out once sitting is not to take a long time to complete a story. Short stories also have a shortening of the constituent elements, so rich in meaning compaction.

3. Research Method

This study uses a quantitative method. The research design is experimental design. In this experimental design there are three designs namely pre-experimental design, true experimental design, and quasi-experimental design. From the three designs the researcher was use true-experimental design. In true-experimental design, there are three designs namely: Pretest-Posttest Control-Group Design, Posttest-Only Control Group-Design, and Solomon Four-Group Design. Based on true-experimental design above, researcher chooses (Pretest-Posttest Control Group-Design) this design involves random assignment of participants to two groups. Both groups are administered both a pretest and a posttest, but the treatment is provided only to experimental group.

In this study, the researcher used test to collect the data. The researcher was gave ten questions to students by using Multiple Choice Completion. In this case, researcher did pretest and posttest to experimental class and control class but the treatment only gave to experimental class. After did the test, the researcher analyze the data by using compare gain for the two groups.

In analyzing the data from the pretest-posttest, the researcher was compare gain scores for the two groups. That is, the mean of 02-01 can be compare with the mean of 04-03 in order to determine whether the treatment had a differential effect on the groups. It is possible to compare the groups on the pretest (01 mean versus the mean for 03). If the groups are equivalent, the posttest means (02 versus 04) can be compared to evaluate the treatment.

4. Discussion

4.1. Experimental Group

In experimental group, researcher gave the pre-test to know the student's ability in vocabulary mastery. The result of pre-test, researcher found the lowest score was 3 and the highest score was 9. In experimental class, researcher gave treatment to find out the different between two classes. The

researcher teaches the short story to experimental class the title is “The fisherman and His Wife”. The score of test student’s vocabulary of experimental class as follow:

No	Rs	Experimental Group	
		Pre-test	Post-test
1	A.D	6	9
2	D.L	9	9
3	D.O	6	8
4	F.N	8	10
5	F.N	5	9
6	F.Y	4	8
7	H.A	3	9
8	I.G	6	8
9	I.S	9	9
10	J.M	5	8
11	J.K	9	10
12	K.L	6	8
13	N.M	9	10
14	R.B	3	7
15	R.T	4	9
16	S.S	6	9
17	S.B	6	7
18	S.A	8	10
19	W.G	5	7
20	Y.G	6	5
Mean:		6,15	8,45

The table above explains about data pretest and posttest in experimental class. Before the researcher analyzes the data, the researcher did test distribution to know the data whether normal or not. And at the result, the data is normal. To make the displayed data cleared, the table of test distribution is displayed below:

Table 2.1 One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test Experimental class

		pretest	posttest
N		20	20
Normal Parameters ^a	Mean	6.15	8.45
	Std. Deviation	1.954	1.276
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.231	.217
	Positive	.231	.133
	Negative	-.128	-.217
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.031	.969
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.238	.304

a. Test distribution is Normal.

Based on the table above, it display that the data is normal. Thus the researcher can continue this research.

To know how the descriptive statistic of pretest, it will be displayed the data below:

Table 2.2 Descriptive Statistics (pretest)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pretest	20	3	9	6.15	1.954
Valid N (listwise)	20				

Based on descriptive statistic data above, it can be described as follow:

The number of students is 20 with a minimum score on pretest is 3 while the maximum score is on pretest is 9. Thus the mean value on the pretest result of SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera is 6, 15 with the standard deviation is 1.954.

The table below will explain about descriptive statistics posttest experimental class.

Table 2.3 Descriptive Statistics (posttest)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Posttest	20	5	10	8.45	1.276
Valid N (listwise)	20				

Based on descriptive statistic data above, it can be described as follow:

The number of students is 20 with a minimum score on posttest is 5 while the maximum score is on pretest is 10. Thus the mean value on the posttest result of SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera is 8,45 with the standard deviation is 1.276.

4.2. Control Group

Before researcher conducted the research, the researcher did pretest in control class to know the students' ability in vocabulary mastery. The result of pre-test was that the students made so many mistakes in vocabulary test. To make the displayed data cleared, the table of students' result of pretest and posttest are displayed below:

No	Rs	Control Group	
		Pre-test	Post-test
1	A.T	6	5
2	A.G	8	9
3	C.R	7	5
4	D.P	8	9
5	D.K.M	5	5
6	E.B	8	10
7	E.Y	7	10
8	F.C.H.R	5	9
9	G.M	6	10
10	H.A	8	10
11	J.N	7	6
12	J.K	7	5
13	K.L	7	10
14	K.H	7	8
15	L.N	7	5
16	L.S	6	7
17	M.B	3	6
18	S.S	9	8
19	S.F.L	6	10
20	Y.D	6	6
Mean:		6,65	7,65

The table above explains about data pretest and posttest in control class.

Before the researcher analyzes the data, the researcher also did test distribution to know the data whether normal or not. And at the result, the data is normal. To make the displayed data cleared, the table of test distribution is displayed below:

		pretest	posttest
	N	20	20
Normal Parameters ^a	Mean	6.65	7.65
	Std. Deviation	1.348	2.084
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.202	.191
	Positive	.148	.186
	Negative	-.202	-.191
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	.905	.856
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.386	.456

a. Test distribution is Normal.

Based on the table above, it display that the data is normal. Thus the researcher can continue this research.

To know how the descriptive statistic of pretest, it will be displayed the data below:

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
pretest	20	3	9	6.65	1.348
Valid N (listwise)	20				

Based on descriptive statistic data above, it can be described as follow:

The number of students is 20 with a minimum score on pretest is 3 while the maximum score on pretest is 9. Thus the mean value on the pretest result of SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera is 6, 65 with the standard deviation is 1.348.

The table below will explain about descriptive statistics posttest control class.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
posttest	20	5	10	7.65	2.084
Valid N (listwise)	20				

Based on descriptive statistic data above, it can be described as follow:

The number of students is 20 with a minimum score on posttest is 5 while the maximum score is on pretest is 10. Thus the mean value on the posttest result of SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera is 7, 65 with the standard deviation are 2.084.

Based on the data above, the researcher found the increase of pretest-posttest control class and pretest-posttest experimental class. In pretest control class the mean value is 6.65 whereas in pretest experimental class is 6, 15. After the researcher did the pretest to control class and experimental class, the researcher also did posttest in control class and experimental class. And the result of posttest, there were improvement it seem from the mean value of the two classes. In class control the mean value is 7, 65 while in experimental class is 8, 45. So, based on these results, the conclusion of the findings is the use of short stories effective can improve students' vocabulary mastery of SMA Kristen Dian Halmahera.

5. Conclusion

Using short story text as a media in learning process, the students were not only required to remember each words, but also expected to master in understanding whole the meaning based on the context. Many students with reading problems have poor vocabularies, and the gap between the vocabularies that they need over time.

Therefore, the vocabulary knowledge also influences someone's skill when students learn a language, especially reading skill. The mastery of vocabulary can support them speaking when they are communicating to people. Students who read the story can translate the meaning to develop a sense of language, and often a love of language skills that will be a benefit all through their lives.

Unfortunately, lack of vocabulary knowledge will result in lack of meaningful communication. It will influence the other language skills, such as speaking, listening, writing, and reading skill.

Having conducted the research, short story was able to improve the quality of English teaching and learning process, especially of vocabulary mastery. Using short story in improving vocabulary mastery the students more easily to understand the words meaning and use the words based on the context. The students also become active, more motivated, more interested, and more enthusiastic in following teaching learning process, so the situation in the class alive. The success can be seen from the category of test in control class and experimental class. The category of pretest control class students' score was 6, 65. The category posttest control class students' score was 7, 65. While the category of pretest experimental class students' score was 6, 15 and the category of posttest experimental class students' score was 8, 45.

Based on result of the test, it shows that there is an improvement of students' vocabulary mastery. Using short story makes the students be active; they know more about words meaning also, how to put the words based on the context. In conclusion, short story can be as problem solving for learning vocabulary.

References

- Hayati. (2015). *Using Short Story to Improve Students' Vocabulary*. Makassar: Universitas Negeri Makassar. <http://eprints.unm.ac.id/929/>
- Hurlock. (1978). *Types of Vocabulary*. Adolescent Development.
- Kridalaksana. (2015). *Word Classes in Indonesia*. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Soedjito. (2011). *Kosa kata bahasa Indonesia*. Malang: Aditya Media Publishing.
- Sugiyono. (2013). *Penelitian kuantitatif dan kualitatif*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sumardjo, J. and Saini, K. M. (1986). *Literature Appreciation. Understanding short story*.

Tarigan, H. G. (2011). *Pengajaran Kosa kata*. Bandung: Angkasa Bandung.